

The titration was continued till the galvanometer reading showed no further decrease on the addition of the reagent. At this stage, the titration was stopped temporarily and the applied potential changed to -1.7 V (vs SCE). The pH was adjusted to 8.0-8.5 and manganese determined following the procedure developed. Typical results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF COPPER AND MANGANESE WITH 2-HANO

Copper (mg)			Manganese (mg)		
Taken	Found	Error %	Taken	Found	Error %
3.006	3.018	+0.88	0.986	0.990	+0.41
2.004	2.013	+0.40	1.972	1.980	+0.41
1.002	1.012	+0.80	2.958	2.966	+0.27

The present study thus shows that manganese can be conveniently determined with 2-HANO as titrant. The results are comparable to those obtained with 1-HANO¹. Literature records no procedure for the simultaneous determination of copper(II) and manganese(II).

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Platinum(II) Heterochelates Derived from Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid and Bidentate NN-Donor Ligands

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ALTHOUGH ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) has been used extensively as a coordinating ligand towards various metal ions¹, very

little has appeared on the platinum(II) complexes of this ligand^{2,3}. Since the report³ of the synthesis of *cis*-dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) in 1956, no work has appeared on the reactivity of this compound towards bidentate ligands. We thought it worthwhile to test the reactivity of the complex and in this note we report the use of the complex as the starting material for the synthesis of platinum(II) heterochelates of the type [Pt(EDTA)(BB)]Cl₂ where BB = ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, propylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, *orthophenanthroline* or 2,2'-bipyridyl.

Experimental

Disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid was purchased from SD's Lab. Chem. Industry. Potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II) and dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) were synthesized by published procedures^{3,4}. Ethylenediamine was a product of Sarabhai M. Chemicals Co. Trimethylenediamine was obtained from Fluka AG (Switzerland). Propylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, 2,2'-bipyridyl and *orthophenanthroline* were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. (U.S.A.).

Analyses and physical measurements of the complexes were carried out as described previously⁵.

General method of synthesis of the complexes :

An aqueous solution of dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) (0.56 g; 1 mmole in 10 ml) was added to an aqueous solution of aliphatic diamine (1 mmole in 15 ml) or an ethanolic solution of aromatic amine (1 mmole in 5 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 30 min with occasional stirring and then cooled in an ice-bath. The separated precipitate was suction filtered, washed with cold water followed by ethanol and dried under vacuum. In case of 2,2'-bipyridyl the compound separated during reflux. All the complexes except [Pt(EDTA)(bipy/phen)]Cl₂ were recrystallized from water. Yield ~60%. The analytical data are given in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The treatment of *cis*-dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) with bidentate ligands (BB) leads to the substitution of two *cis*-chloride ions by one molecule of BB and heterochelates of the type [Pt(EDTA)(BB)]Cl₂ are formed. The electrolytic conductance measurements in water indicate bi-univalent nature of the complexes ($\Lambda_M = 215-229$ ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹)⁶. The complexes are diamagnetic indicating square planar structure of the complexes.

In the ir spectra of the complexes the strong band in the range 1690-1695 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the non-coordinated carboxyl carbonyl group of EDTA moiety⁷. The presence of this band in *cis*-dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) and in the heterochelates indicates that EDTA is behaving as a bidentate ligand and the four carboxylic acid

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF PLATINUM(II) COMPLEXES*

Complex/Stoichiometry	Colour	Λ_M $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ cm^2	Anal. sis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					ν_{max} $\text{cm}^{-1}(\epsilon)$
			Pt	N	Cl	C	H	
[Pt(EDTA)en]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Lemon yellow	225.8	31.4 (81.55)	8.8 (9.06)	11.2 (11.49)	28.4 (28.30)	3.9 (3.88)	50000(17140), 37740(10020), 30779(62)
[Pt(EDTA)tn]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Yellow	215.1	31.1 (80.85)	8.9 (8.86)	11.0 (11.28)	24.8 (24.68)	4.2 (4.11)	
[Pt(EDTA)pn]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Light yellow	228.3	30.5 (80.85)	8.9 (8.86)	10.9 (11.28)	24.2 (24.68)	4.3 (4.11)	
[Pt(EDTA)apy]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Light yellow	229.2	29.3 (29.91)	8.7 (8.69)	10.6 (10.89)	27.4 (27.61)	3.2 (3.37)	50000(17760). 39220(10640). 30770(1705)
[Pt(EDTA)bipy]Cl ₂ C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Reddish yellow	a	28.0 (27.81)	7.6 (7.84)	9.4 (9.94)	38.7 (38.61)	3.4 (3.86)	
[Pt(EDTA)phen]Cl ₂ C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Lemon yellow	a	26.3 (26.42)	7.2 (7.59)	9.2 (9.62)	35.7 (35.77)	3.1 (3.25)	

a Conductance could not be measured due to low solubility of the compound in water.

* Abbreviations : en = ethylenediamine, tn = trimethylenediamine, pn = propylenediamine, apy = 3-aminopyridine, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl and phen = orthophenanthroline.

groups are free. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (ring) stretch of 2,2'-bipyridyl, orthophenanthroline and 3-aminopyridine occurs at 1582, 1558 and 1590 cm^{-1} , respectively^{7,8}. In the complexes, this band undergoes a positive shift by 30-38 cm^{-1} . This is indicative of nitrogen coordination of these ligands. The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ vibration of ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, propylenediamine and 3-aminopyridine occurs at 1620, 1620, 1620 and 1590 cm^{-1} , respectively^{8,9}. In the platinum(II) complexes this band shifts to lower wave number by 10-45 cm^{-1} . This indicates the nitrogen coordination of these amines. Thus, the complexes are straightforward four-coordinate.

The electronic spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes exhibit three bands around 30000, 38000 and 50000 cm^{-1} . Only in the ethylenediamine complex the first band has low molar extinction coefficient (52 litre $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and this band can be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ transition. The molar extinction coefficients of other bands are very high and these bands may be assigned to intraligand, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions¹⁰.

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Screening of Metal Complexes for Biological Activity. Part V : Synthesis and Biological Studies on Zinc(II) Complexes with Various Amides

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BIOCHEMICAL and medicinal significance of simple zinc(II) complexes has been discussed by many workers¹⁻³. However, coordination complexes of zinc(II) are yet to be subjected to these studies. So, as a part of our investigation on synthesis of biologically active metal complexes⁴⁻⁵, we report here preparation, characterization and a few pharmacological aspects viz., toxicity and effects on central nervous system (CNS) of some zinc(II) complexes of nicotinamide (nic), N-methyl-propanamide (Nmpa) and benzamide (bza).

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